

Speculation on Energy and Potential Energy and Their Direct Link to Force Part 2

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In Part 1, we suggested that $\exp(ipx)$ represents a spatial probability for the rendering of momentum hits. A single particle has a center-of-mass which undergoes $x=vt$, but momentum hits are not rendered from this point, but are rather delivered in x according to the complex probability $\exp(ipx)$ which is linked with the resolution $\Delta x = \hbar/p$. This accounts for the fact that a particle can probabilistically interact with each slit of a 2-slit apparatus if they are about $\hbar/apart$. If one is only interested in energy, $p^2/2m$, the classical result holds for both $\exp(-ipx)$ and $\exp(ipx)$. In a classical bound state, one considers only energy $p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x)=E$ because each $p(x)$ exists at x in $dx \rightarrow 0$. One cannot distinguish any probabilistic hit distribution. $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ differ even though they are linked with the same kinetic energy $p^2/2m$ (nonrelativistic case). We argued in Part 1, that the Newtonian conservation of energy equation actually includes a force profile linked with $V(x)$. The catch is that for $V(x)$ one has a force at each x , $dx \rightarrow 0$. Such is not the case for $\exp(ipx)$. We argued in Part 1 that one must consider not only $p^2/2m$, but the associated spatial probability distribution for hits (i.e. energy together with force).

Here, we note that this idea gives rise to an equilibrium calculation. This is somewhat startling because classically, and even quantum mechanically for higher energy levels, a particle moves to the right part of the time and then to the left for other times. As a result, a calculation which respects time would not average over $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$. Only an equilibrium calculation in time would do so. We suggest that one must consider the Newtonian conservation of energy equation as applying to both $p(x)$ and $-p(x)$ and so from an energy point of view one may consider it to be an average. The catch is that each term $p(x)$ and $-p(x)$ yields the same kinetic energy profile in the Newtonian case and the same $V(x)$.

For a quantum particle the kinetic energy with probabilistic force distribution is not the same for p and $-p$. As a result, to use $V(x)$ which applies to forward and backwards motion, one is forced to consider the average and this leads to an equilibrium scenario. We show that the average kinetic with probabilistic force hit profile in space is not the same for $+p$ and $-p$. Measurements, however, take time and may be averages of much data and so the notion of an average or equilibrium seems to make sense. We note, however, that an average is very different from the Newtonian forwards-backwards motion picture. Only in the high energy limit does the energy $p^2/2m$ with probabilistic force profile become the same for both p and $-p$. Thus, the main point of this note is to stress the notion of a single particle bound state as an average and to point out the consequences of this.

Quantum Mechanics of a Free Particle

A quantum mechanical free particle has a kinetic energy (nonrelativistic case) of $p^2/2m$ which is completely classical. This notion is retained in quantum single particle bound state calculations at any energy level, implying that quantum mechanics does not exist separated from classical ideas. The difference with a quantum free particle, we argue, is that it does not render its impulse hit at the center-of-mass point which moves as:

$$x=vt \quad ((1))$$

Rather, it renders momentum impulse hits in space in a probabilistic manner described by a complex probability:

$$\exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

The complex probability has the same modulus for any p showing that $x=vt$ for any v is associated with $P(x)dx=dx/L$, where L is an arbitrary length.

The question then becomes: What can one do with ((2))? One can use it to describe one dimensional single particle reflection-refraction at an n_1 - n_2 (index of refraction junction) or the interaction at a 2-slit apparatus (separation of slits about \hbar/p). $\exp(ipx)$ is a mathematical probability and describes probabilistic interaction and so can be used in such calculations.

Classical Bound State Problem

A classical bound state problem is linked with the conservation of energy equation:

$$p(x)p(x)/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((3))$$

In Part 1, we noted that even though this has the appearance of a strictly energy equation at each x , one must take into account the notion of force $-dV/dx$. This force acts in a tiny $dx \rightarrow 0$ at each x which changes $p(x)$. Even in the conservation of energy picture, one cannot escape thinking of force. $\exp(ipx)$ is the quantum probability in space for impulse hits and these cannot be confined to $dx \rightarrow 0$, but are rather linked with \hbar/p . Each p , however, represents a classical energy of $pp/2m$ (nonrelativistic). One must then average various $\exp(ipx)pp/2m$ terms to try to obtain an average kinetic energy. In a classical bound problem, $p(x)$ and $-p(x)$ have the same energy and same impulse hit range $dx \rightarrow 0$ (although the sign of the force differs). This is not the case for a quantum $\exp(ipx)$. This leads to a problem. If one wishes to consider both energy $pp/2m$ and a force profile together, then strict motion to the right does not match strict motion to the left as we show.

Quantum Kinetic Energy for Strict Forwards and Backwards Motion

Traditionally, one considers an equilibrium (average over time) for a single particle average kinetic energy, i.e.

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \} \quad ((4))$$

Physically, however, a particle either moves to the right or left classically and even quantum mechanically, at least for fairly high energy levels. At low energy levels there is large uncertainty in x position with respect to the system length and so it is not really clear if the particle is at one x or another or if it has already reflected at the turning and is moving in the opposite direction.

If one tries to separate forwards and backwards motion and calculate the average KE, then:

$$\text{Forwards motion: } KE_{+ave}(x) = [\{ \sum a(p) \cos(px) \} \{ \sum a(p) p^2/m \cos(px) \} - i \{ \sum p^2/m \sin(px) a(p) \} \{ \sum a(p) \cos(px) \} + \{ \sum p^2/m a(p) \sin(px) \} \{ \sum a(p) \sin(px) \}] / G(x) \quad ((5a))$$

$$\text{where } G(x) = \{ \sum a(p) \cos(px) \} \{ \sum a(p) \cos(px) \} + \{ \sum a(p) \sin(px) \} \{ \sum a(p) \sin(px) \} \quad ((5b))$$

and Backwards motion $KE_{-ave}(x)$ is obtained by replacing p with $-p$ in ((5a)) to obtain ((5c))

The point we make is that these two average kinetic energies with probabilistic force profiles are not the same. To see this specifically, consider only two p values p_1 , and p_2 and imagine that they are tiny . Then:

$$\begin{aligned} & \{ p_1 p_1/2m a(p_1) \exp(ip_1 x) + p_2 p_2/2m a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x) \} / \{ a(p_1) \exp(ip_1 x) + a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x) \} \\ & = \{ p_1 p_1/2m a(p_1) (1+ip_1 x) + p_2 p_2/2m a(p_2) (1+ip_2 x) \} / \{ a(p_1) (1+ip_1 x) + a(p_2) (1+ip_2 x) \} \end{aligned}$$

If one multiplies numerator and denominator by $[a(p_1)+a(p_2)] - i(p_1+p_2)x$, one has for the real part of the numerator

$$((p_1 p_1/2m a(p_1) + p_2 p_2/2m a(p_2)) [a(p_1)+a(p_2)] + \{ p_1 p_1/2m a(p_1) p_1 x (p_1+p_2)x + p_2 p_2/2m a(p_2) p_2 x (p_1+p_2)x \}) \text{ for the real part } \quad ((6a))$$

If $a(p)=a(-p)$, then $p \rightarrow -p$ does not change the real part of the numerator.

For the imaginary part of the numerator, however, one has:

$$(p_1 p_1/2m a(p_1) p_1 x (a(p_1)+a(p_2)) + p_2 p_2/2m a(p_2) p_2 x (a(p_1)+a(p_2)) - (p_1+p_2)x (p_1 p_1/2m a(p_1) + p_2 p_2/2m a(p_2))) \quad ((6b))$$

One may see that for $p \rightarrow -p$, that the imaginary part of average kinetic energy changes sign. Furthermore, one does not want to have an imaginary kinetic energy in an energy conservation equation. Thus, one is forced to average over forward and negative motion in order that imaginary kinetic energy disappear and one deals with the completely real equation:

$$\{ \sum \text{over } p a(p) p^2/m \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \sum \text{over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((7))$$

((7)), however, is an average equation and must be understood as one. Physically, a particle may move back and forth in quantum energy levels that are somewhat high. Physically, one would not expect to average over time like this, but one does not simply deal with energy $p^2/2m$, but with probabilistic impulse hit rendering in such an equation and the average equation creates an equilibrium scenario.

Zero Points for Average $W(x)$

The above approach creates a real function $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ which has crests and troughs yielding 0 points for $W(x)$. This does not mean that the particle cannot appear at these points. One has an average over $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$, but physically the particle either moves to the right or left (especially for high energies) and so the average quantity is simply that, an average, not a statement that the quantum particle cannot be found at 0 points. On average, however, it is as if the particle is avoiding these average points and so on average, there is in fact an impulse hit spatial density given by:

$$W(x)W(x) \quad ((8))$$

We suggest, however, that this must be understood in terms of an average, i.e. equilibrium for the very reason that even the average of a number $pp/2m$ is associated with different $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ impulse hit probabilities in space.

The Importance of Impulse Hit Distributions

The term $W(x)W(x)$ represents the spatial equilibrium impulse hit distribution. As a result, a particle may have an average $KE(x)$ equilibrium at x , but on average the particle may avoid a zero point and so one should multiply $KE(x)$ by $W(x)W(x)$. We note that in a quantum bound state one also has:

$$\{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx)\} / \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)\} = .5 m \ v_{rms} \ v_{rms} \quad ((9))$$

V_{rms} may be used to calculate a kind of Δt at each Δx , but this is not the probability for the particle to render an impulse hit at x . It is $W(x)W(x)$ which gives this value, but for an equilibrium scenario which is also not the physical picture which occurs, at least for somewhat high energy levels.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part 1 we noted that quantum mechanics associates a classical kinetic energy value $pp/2m$ with a probability for rendering an impulse hit in space of $\exp(ipx)$. By using this probability $\exp(ipx)$ to calculate an average $pp/2m$ means that one is really averaging over an impulse hit distribution in x , i.e. thinking of force in space even as one considers energy conservation. In Part 2, we show that the impulse hit distributions are not the same for p and $-p$ which leads to a big problem if one wishes to balance a number, namely energy. One is forced to consider an equilibrium scenario which includes $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ even when physically for high energy levels the quantum bound particle moves to the right and then to the left, like a classical one. It is only the equilibrium viewpoint which allows one to create $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ as a real function and use $KE_{ave}(x)+V(x)=E_n$. This means that $W(x)W(x)$ must also be viewed as an average impulse hit rendering spatial density. Zeros of $W(x)W(x)$ and hence $W(x)$ do not mean that the particle cannot appear at these points, rather it means that on

average (considering p and $-p$) the impulse hit average probability tends to 0 or is low. Thus, a quantum bound state calculation is very much an average one and has to be in order to use the real valued $V(x)$ and E .